

Violence: Types, Distribution, and Frequency. A Study on the Re-concentration of Homicides in the City of Rosario, Argentina (2007-2023)

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Abstract

This paper is part of my doctoral thesis project: “Urban development policies and police-criminal regulation, illegal markets and violence. A comparative study on the intensification and distribution of violence in Córdoba and Rosario (2007-2023)” directed by Dr. Paul Hathazy. In this presentation, I analyze the reconcentration of homicidal criminal violence in the city of Rosario, according to its typologies, frequency, location and evolution.

For several years, violence has become a topic of public debate and an area of intervention involving various actors that influence the intervention agenda (Luneke and Varela, 2020). Part of this reflection has been aimed at trying to explain the differences in the distribution of violence, which shows patterns of concentration in some areas such as Latin America. Within the academic field, we are witnessing a growing interest in violence, which in the last decade has become an emerging field of research within sociology (Walby, 2012).

We define violence from the contributions of Malesevic (2020:23) as “a gradual social process in which individuals, groups and social organizations are immersed in situations in which their intentional or unintentional actions generate substantial changes in behaviors imposed under coercion or the production of physical, mental, emotional, injury or death”. This definition has the virtue of focusing on organized forms of violence. We articulate this perspective with the developments of Randall Collins (2009, 2012), for whom the use of physical force is a necessary component in the definition of violence and is what makes it possible to identify its specificity. His work highlights the micro-interactional mechanisms of confrontation, through the notion of “confrontational tension and fear (ct/f)” (Collins, 2012, p. 135) to analyze the barriers that make it possible to explain why violence often fails and why it is generally incompetent, as well as the factors that make violence successful. This perspective allows us to consider the dynamics at work among different types of interpersonal violence.

If we take only homicide rates, we find that Latin America and the Caribbean (LAC) is the most violent region in the world, far exceeding the rates in Africa (12.7), Europe (2.2), Oceania (2.9), Asia (2.3) and North America (5.3) (UNODC, 2023). During 2023 in the region, 117,492 people were murdered, resulting in a rate of 17.8 homicides per 100,000 inhabitants (Newton, 2024), 81% of which were carried out using firearms (United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime, 2023). Argentina has a low homicide rate compared to other countries in the region. However, the deaths that occur in the country are not evenly distributed. In some cities (and especially in some neighborhoods), homicide rates are higher than average. Rosario, particularly “suffered a dramatic increase in homicides in just three years, [going] from 10 per hundred thousand inhabitants in 2010 to 22 per hundred thousand in 2013.” (Bergman, 2022, p.42).

When considering the distribution of homicides within large cities we find in the literature that “a distinctive feature is their ‘spatial heterogeneity’ (Bergman, 2022) as murders are concentrated in certain regions, and even on certain streets. [...] (Bergman, 2022, p.41-42). We anticipate that our analysis shows that in the case of Rosario, there was a shift from a pattern of greater dispersion to one of territorial concentration, detecting a focalization of deaths in a few neighborhoods of the city. However, several studies have conducted geo-referenced analyses of homicides. This analysis is distinguished by the attempt to produce not only a description of homicidal criminal violence, but also to produce typologies that allow us to distinguish between different types of violence. Tentatively, we distinguish between:

- Type of violent interactions:

1. Individual: violent interactions in which one person causes physical harm to others or others, without the direct influence of a group.
2. Group (group effect): violent interactions that occur as a result of the dynamics of a group, whether gangs, criminal organizations, or collective events.

- Dynamics:

1. Spontaneous: violent interactions that occur without prior planning, often as a result of the micro situational context, escalation of the confrontation, presence of witnesses, and other elements described by Collins (2004). Although, descriptively we incorporate this classification to individual violence, it is central to distinguish between forms of group violence by individuals not belonging to groups engaged in organized violence.

2. Organized: these are violent interactions that require a certain amount of planning and are linked to membership in organized groups that, due to their characteristics, have the capacity to coerce or produce physical, mental or emotional harm, injury or death. Among these we find groups linked to organized crime, police organizations, drug trafficking gangs and hired assassins. A characteristic of these groups is a certain habituation to the use of violence as part of their action scheme, so that the cf/t barriers (Collins,) do not operate in the same way as in those who are not part of these groups.

- Reasons:

1. Disputes over territorial or neighborhood honor.
2. Family honor disputes
3. Predatory violence (robberies)
4. Confrontation for territorial dominion, here we distinguish between those linked to legal markets, drug markets and other illegal markets.
5. Interpersonal conflicts (fights, personal honor).
6. Violence due to hired killings
7. Community conflicts (lynching, confrontations)
8. Neighborhood disputes

The methodology we used in this work is quantitative, longitudinal through a trend analysis. The data production (homicide database for the city of Rosario) was carried out using web scraping tools in R language. The analysis and cleaning of the data was also carried out using this language, while the body of the news was analyzed using the open source artificial intelligence tool Ollama. The visualization of the georeferenced data was carried out using QGIS, while the production of graphs to accompany the paper was carried out using the R library ggplot.